

THE ROLE OF POTTERY ART IN TRAINING STUDENTS IN PROFESSIONALS

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After our republic gained independence, as in all spheres, significant changes have occurred in the field of handicrafts. The Decree “On measures to support the further development of folk arts and crafts and applied arts by the state” published on March 31, 1997 is a clear proof of this. According to this Decree, it was determined that artisans are exempt from state taxes, can sell their products at a free price, participate in international exhibitions, participate in artistic organizations, and carry out creative work abroad.

Handicrafts are an important type of modern division of labor in the development of urban life. Handicrafts are a process directly related to trade and are carried out in densely populated areas. It is known that the values and traditions of applied arts play a special role in teaching young people a profession. As a craftsman teaches his apprentices the secrets of the craft, he teaches them certain educational qualities, including earning money through honest work, enduring failures, not only increasing wealth through their craft, but also contributing to the development of society, completing what they have started, using economic knowledge and concepts to develop entrepreneurial and business skills, and speaking the truth.

No matter what profession there is in the world, there will be masters and apprentices for it. Crafts such as painting, carpentry, coppersmithing, knifemaking, mat making, carpet making, woodcarving, and basket making have their own masters. A master who specializes in coppersmithing is called a coppersmith, a master who specializes in painting is called a painter, and among these, there are carpentry, mat making, basket making, blacksmithing, bone carving, barbering, jeweler, woodcarver, and other crafts. In ancient times, crafts and natural knowledge were not taught in schools, but were taught individually. For example:

– mastering the craft of a father or mother – from parents, adults in the family, as an individual apprentice;

- as an individual apprentice to a master;
- that is, in organized workshops, workshops, as an individual apprentice.

In ancient times, each craft was considered sacred, respected and revered. Our ancestors developed their own etiquette, special laws, customs, and culture for teachers and students, and these rules were strictly observed. There were special rituals, prayers, and national traditions in the teacher-student relationship. Both the teacher and the student had their own tasks and duties. The professional culture of a craftsman includes the following:

- learning the craft not for the purpose of gaining wealth, but to contribute to the development of society as a whole;
- protecting the craft from unearned income;
- respecting the authority of teachers;
- seeking the consent of elders;
- receiving the blessings of elders;
- not being lazy in work;
- being hardworking and honest in work;
- being disciplined;
- not being discouraged by failure;
- being a wise entrepreneur in the craft;
- being clean;
- not moving on to another job without completing it.

Characteristics that a craftsman should know:

- not having contact with those who gain wealth through unclean means;
- Hostility and envy towards other professions, inability to see the success of others;
- cowardice, laziness, laziness, frivolity, wastefulness, arrogance, deceit.

The professional qualities of a teacher include his interest in his profession, his sincere teaching of his profession to young people, his introduction of innovations into his profession, leaving behind good, loyal students in this profession, and others. In the past, parents also respected and honored the teacher who taught their children the profession. The culture of relations between parents and teachers also had its own character. They consisted of the following moral concepts:

Parents' attitude towards the teacher:

- showing kindness to the teacher;
- correctly understanding the teacher's reprimand;

- to provide the child with the necessary things by learning a trade;
- to please the teacher.

The teacher also had a special attitude towards the parents. They are as follows:

- to fulfill the task he undertook to teach the child a trade;
- to fulfill his promise;
- to speak openly to parents about their child's abilities and behavior.

All of the above information is taken from S. Bulatov's scientific article "Personal and Professional Qualities of a Teacher". S. Bulatov's information about the traditions, customs and traditions of the teacher-student relationship in Uzbek applied decorative art was analyzed in detail from a scientific and theoretical perspective in a large-scale fundamental scientific research work entitled "Uzbek folk applied decorative art" with a volume of about 60 printed plates. This scientific research work reflects the history, characteristics of all types of Uzbek folk applied decorative art, and illustrative materials classifying them. However, some types of art was presented in a popular manner, and the pedagogical and methodological aspects of the issue were not fully covered [S. Bulatov. 24].

Nevertheless, this scientific research work serves as the main source for further scientific research. The talented scientist S. Bulatov, together with his students, is conducting scientific research on the problems of studying Uzbek crafts, on the history, ethnography, philosophical, spiritual, educational aspects of applied art.

In today's education system, providing artistic education to young people through folk applied art has its own unique aspects, which, in turn, is of great importance in educating young people as complete people. Because the content of applied art embodies our long past, national heritage, national traditions. Therefore, its importance in general education institutions is especially significant. Therefore, the problems of artistic education and upbringing have also played a significant role in the formation of a spiritually harmonious generation, taking into account universal human and national values, the creative experiences of our ancestors, and centuries-old traditions. The high human qualities of young people, their interest in the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, and one or another innate ability in them can be effectively formed in their youth. In this regard, folk applied art acquires a special essence. The traditions of all nations and peoples of the world have spiritual and material values. The spiritual world of each nation and people is reflected in its moral standards, customs and traditions and affects the spiritual formation of the individual.

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